

SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE FORMATION OF CLINICAL TERMS IN LATIN

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ABSTRACT: This article presents some ideas on the formation of clinical terms in Latin based on examples. It provides information on the formation and meaning of clinical terms, mainly with the help of suffixes.

KEY WORDS: suffixes, term elements, prefix, clinical terms, traditional, pathological conditions

The study of clinical terminology in Latin classes is based on the analysis of individual components, called term elements. A term element is a word-forming element (root, stem, prefix, suffix), which, having a constant meaning, forms a term of one semantic series.

Suffixes have an important classifying function, some of them have acquired a clearly defined terminological meaning. It is by the presence of one or another suffix that we attribute nouns or adjectives to certain groups.

A distinctive feature of the suffixes of clinical terms is their semantics, i.e., they convey meanings that are characteristic only of this terminology.

Suffixes in clinical terminology usually act as final TEs, connecting with or without noun endings. In clinical terminology, four suffixes are widely used, such as -osis, -iasis, -itis, -ismus, -oma, which have certain terminological concepts.

One of the most common suffixes in clinical terminology is -itis, itīdis f. It was first used by the French physician François Sauvage (mid-18th century) to create the term peritonitis, itīdis f. Then in 1800 the term bronchitis, itīdis f. was formed. Since then, the suffix has become the most productive in clinical terminology and has formed a microsystem of names for inflammatory diseases. If the integumentary membrane of the organ is affected by inflammation, the prefix peri- is added to the clinical term: perimetritis, itīdis f - inflammation of the peritoneum covering the uterus; if the fiber is around the organ - the prefix para-: parametritis, itīdis f - inflammation of the fiber near the uterus; if the inner shell of the organ is the prefix endo-: endometritis, itīdis f - inflammation of the uterine mucosa.

Terms with this suffix are unequal feminine nouns of the third declension. Some inflammatory diseases retain their traditional names: pneumonia - inflammation of the lungs, paronychia - acute purulent inflammation of the periungual tissues of the fingers.

The suffix -oma attached to the stem of a tissue name forms the names of tumors that arise from this tissue: fibrōma, ātis n - a benign tumor of fibrous connective tissue; osteōma, ātis n is a benign bone tumor.

Malignant tumors of some tissues have traditional names: carcinōma - a cancerous tumor, carcinoma; cancer - a malignant tumor from the epithelium; sarcōma - a malignant tumor of mesenchymal origin (from the Greek sarcōma - a fleshy growth, tumor).

The suffix *ōma* is also used in certain names of diseases not associated with tumors: *glaucōma*, *ātis n* - an eye disease characterized by increased intraocular pressure.

In clinical terms, the suffix *-ēma* also occurs. It does not have a clear motivational basis and is found in the names of various diseases: *emphysēma*, *ātis n* - expansion of air space in the lungs; *empyēma*, *ātis n* - accumulation of pus in a natural cavity; *erythēma*, *ātis n* - limited or diffuse reddening of the skin due to hyperemia, sometimes with the formation of nodes.

Terms with suffixes *-ōma*, *-ēma* are neuter nouns of the third declension.

The suffix *-ōsis*, has the general meaning "pathological process, disease of a non-inflammatory nature": *nephrosīs*, *is f* - degenerative disease of the renal tubules; *arteriosclerōsis*, *is f* - sclerosis of arterial vessels.

If the base denotes a blood cell or a tumor, then the terms acquire the meaning of "an increase in the number, a multiplicity of manifestations": *leucocytōsis*, *is f* - an increase in the number of leukocytes in the blood; *angiomatōsis*, *is f* - multiple angiomas.

The suffix *-ōsis* is also included in many clinical terms of general content, performing a purely derivational function: *diagnōsis*, *is f* - diagnosis, recognition of the disease; *prognōsis*, *is f* - forecast, foresight of the development of events (lit. "preliminary knowledge"); *anastomōsis*, *is f* - connection of two tubular organs.

Terms with the suffix *-osis* are equivalent nouns of the third declension of the feminine.

The suffix *-iāsis* denotes diseases of a non-inflammatory nature with a long course: *nephrolithiasis*, *is f* - nephrolithiasis; *psoriāsis*, *is f* - skin disease. Terms with this suffix are equivalent nouns of the third declension of the feminine.

The suffix *-ismus* denotes a phenomenon, property, fact, marked by a sign called the basis: *infantilismus*, *i m* - underdevelopment of the body, stopped at a childish degree of bodily or mental development (*infans*, *ntis m, f* - child, child); *alcoholismus*, *i m* - excessive use of alcoholic beverages and addiction to them. One-word clinical terms are formed in an affixed and non-affixed way. The affixing method is suffixing (attaching a suffix to the stem) and prefixing (attaching a prefix to the root). Terms formed in an affixal way are called derivatives.

Clinical terminology includes terminological names of diseases and pathological conditions, methods of treatment and examination of patients, names of medical instruments.

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